

Chalkones Part III

Synthesis of Some Cyanochalkones and their Reactions.

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A number of benzaldehydes were condensed with *o*-, *m*- and *p*- cyanoacetophenones to give the corresponding chalkones. Some of the reactions of cyanochalkones leading to the formation of different heterocyclic compounds have been studied. The condensation of chalkones with cyclohexanone has also been studied.

The present work is an extension of an earlier work^{1,2} and describes the condensation of different benzaldehydes with *p*-, *m*-, and *o*- cyanoacetophenones. It was observed that *p*- and *m*- cyanoacetophenones reacted without difficulty with the different aldehydes to give the corresponding chalkones, but *o*-cyanoacetophenone reacted with difficulty.

Some of the addition reactions of chalkones with ethyl acetoacetate, β -amino- β -methyl-acrylonitriles, phenylhydrazines and indole have been reported here.

2-Methyl-4'-cyanochalkone was condensed with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate to give I.

2-Methyl-4'-cyanochalkone and 2-methyl-3'-cyanochalkone were condensed with 3-aminobutyronitrile³ to give IIa and IIb respectively. Heating IIa in a sealed tube with concentrated hydrochloric acid at 190° gave the diacid IIc.

1. J. R. Merchant and A. S. U. Choughuley, *Chem. Ber.*, 1962, **95**, 1792.
2. J. R. Merchant, V. B. Desai and J. B. Mehta, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 561.
3. H. Adkins and K. K. Whitman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 152.

Phenylhydrazine on condensation^{3a} with 2-methyl-4'-cyanochalkone, 3,4,5-trimethoxy-4'-cyanochalkone, 2-chloro-3'-cyanochalkone and 2,4'-dimethoxy-5-bromo-3'-cyanochalkone afforded the corresponding pyrazolines IIIa (R = 2-methyl; R₁ = 4'-cyano); IIIb (R = 3,4,5-trimethoxy; R₁ = 4'-cyano); IIIc (R = 2-chloro; R₁ = 3'-cyano) and IIId (R = 2,4-dimethoxy-5-bromo; R₁ = 3'-cyano) respectively.

The expected addition products IVa (R = 2-methyl; R₁ = 4'-cyano), IVb (R = 3-ethoxy-4-methoxy; R₁ = 4'-cyano) and IVc (R = 2-methyl; R₁ = 3'-cyano) were also obtained by the reaction of 2-methyl-4'-cyanochalkone, 3-ethoxy-4-methoxy-4'-cyanochalkone and 2-methyl-3'-cyanochalkone with indole.

4-Methoxy-4'-methylchalkone was condensed² with cyclohexanone to give V which was cyclised to VI. The lactam derivative VII was prepared as before from its oxime. The lactam VII on boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid afforded the hydrochloride VIIIa which was converted to the free base VIIIb by treatment with alkali.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of o-cyanoacetophenone with anisaldehyde: Formation of 4-methoxy-2'-cyanochalkone: To a solution of *o*-cyanoacetophenone (300 mg) and anisaldehyde (220 mg) in alcohol (5 ml) was added three drops of 10% sodium hydroxide with shaking. The colour changed from yellow to deep red and slowly a yellow solid started separating. After 20 min. the solid (100 mg) was filtered, washed repeatedly with water and crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 108°. (Found C, 77.2; H, 5.1; N, 5.3. C₁₇H₁₃NO₂ requires C, 77.6; H, 5.3; N, 5.2%).

With *o*-methylbenzaldehyde, 2-methyl-2'-cyanochalkone was obtained in light yellow plates m.p. 159° (Found: C, 82.4; H, 5.5; N, 5.3. C₁₇H₁₃NO requires C, 82.6; H, 5.3; N, 5.7%).

TABLE I
 Showing the condensation of *p*-cyanoacetophenone with different aldehydes†

Benzaldehyde	Chalkone	m.p.	Physical State	Percentage Analysis					
				Calculated			Found		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
2-Chloro	2-Chloro-4'-cyano (1)	236°	White needles	71.91	3.74	5.24	71.7	3.69	5.4
2,4-Dichloro	2,4-Dichloro-4'-cyano (2)	260°	White granules*	63.57	2.98	4.65	63.6	3.3	4.8
2-Methyl	2-Methyl-4'-cyano (3)	170°	Light yellow plates	82.57	5.3	5.66	82.4	5.5	5.8
4-Dimethylamino	4-Dimethylamino-4'-cyano (4)	165°	Reddish brown plates**	78.23	5.84	10.14	77.8	5.7	10.4
2-Ethoxy-3-methoxy	2-Ethoxy-3-methoxy-4'-cyano (5)	140°	Yellow needles	74.25	5.58	4.56	74.4	5.7	4.9
3-Ethoxy-4-methoxy	3-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-4'-cyano (6)	133°	Yellow silky needles	74.25	5.58	4.56	74.0	5.3	4.4
2,4-Dimethoxy-5-bromo	2,4-Dimethoxy-5-bromo-4'-cyano (7)	212°	Yellow needles***	58.06	3.75	3.75	58.2	3.9	4.1
3,4,5-Trimethoxy	3,4,5-Trimethoxy-4'-cyano (8)	180°	Bright yellow needles***	70.58	5.3	4.33	70.8	5.6	4.2
4-Benzoyloxy	4-Benzoyloxy-4'-cyano (9)	153°	White needles	81.39	5.05	4.13	81.5	5.3	3.88
2,4-Dibenzoyloxy	2,4-Dibenzoyloxy-4'-cyano (10)	203°	White needles	80.88	5.2	3.14	81.1	5.4	3.0
Cinnamaldehyde	Cinnamalidene-4'-cyano (11)	142°	Bright yellow plates	83.38	5.05	5.4	83.7	5.4	5.4

† Prepared as reported². Optimum yields 40-50%.

* Crystallised from acetic acid.

** Crystallised from dilute methanol. All other cyanochalkones are crystallised from ethyl alcohol.

*** 10% Potassium hydroxide is used as condensing agent. All other cyanochalkones are synthesised by using 10% sodium hydroxide.

TABLE II
Showing the condensation of m-cyanoacetophenone with different aldehydes†

Benzaldehyde	Chalkone	m.p.	Physical State	Percentage Analysis					
				Calculated			Found		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
2-Chloro	2-Chloro-3'-cyano (12)	133°	White needles	71.91	3.74	5.24	72.0	3.9	5.2
2,4-Dichloro	2,4-Dichloro-3'-cyano (13)	153°	White granules	63.57	2.98	4.65	63.6	3.3	4.4
2-Methyl	2-Methyl-3'-cyano (14)	154°	Light yellow needles	82.57	5.3	5.66	82.3	5.1	5.3
3-Ethoxy-4-methoxy	3-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-3'-cyano (15)	145°	Yellow needles	74.25	5.58	4.56	74.1	5.8	4.6
2,4-Dimethoxy-5-bromo	2,4-Dimethoxy-5-bromo-3'-cyano (16)	196°	Yellow needles*	58.06	3.75	3.76	57.9	3.7	3.9
3,4-Dimethoxy-5-iodo	3,4-Dimethoxy-5-iodo-3'-cyano (17)	193°	Yellow granules*	-	-	3.4	-	-	3.7
4-Benzoyloxy	4-Benzoyloxy-3'-cyano (18)	163°	Yellow plates	81.39	5.05	4.13	81.3	4.8	4.4
2,4-Dibenzoyloxy	2,4-Dibenzoyloxy-3'-cyano (19)	128°	White needles	80.88	5.2	3.14	80.5	5.4	3.2
3,4,5-Trimethoxy	3,4,5-Trimethoxy-3'-cyano (20)	156°	Bright yellow needles*	70.58	5.3	4.33	70.3	5.7	4.7

† Prepared as reported². Optimum yields 40-50%.

* 10% potassium hydroxide is used as condensing agent. All other cyanochalkones are synthesised by using 10% sodium hydroxide.

TABLE III

Chalkone (g.)	Reactant (g.)	Product obtained (mg.)	Solvent and shape of crystals	Analysis					
				Required			Found		
		m.p.		C	H	N	C	H	N
2-Methyl-4'-cyano- (200)	Ethyl acetate 3-4 drops	I (80)	dilute alcohol, thin plates	76.9	5.9	3.9	76.9	5.7	3.7
2-Methyl-4'-cyano- (1.25)	3-aminobutyronitrile (.720)	IIa	benzene, light yellow needles	81.5	4.9	13.6	81.3	4.7	13.3
2-Methyl-3'-cyano- (1.25)	3-aminobutyronitrile (.720)	IIb	benzene, light yellow needles	81.5	4.9	13.6	81.6	4.8	13.7
2-Methyl-4'-cyano- (.500)	Phenylhydrazine (.500)	IIIa (600)	ethyl alcohol, light yellow needles	81.87	5.7	12.5	81.8	5.8	12.8
3,4,5-Trimethoxy-4'-cyano- (1.0)	-do- (1.0)	IIIb (500)	ethyl alcohol	72.6	5.6	10.2	72.8	5.7	10.4
2-Chloro-3'-cyano- (1.0)	-do- (1.0)	IIIc (200)	ethyl alcohol	74.0	4.4		73.8	4.4	
2,4-Dimethoxy-5-bromo-3'-cyano- (.500)	-do- (.500)	IIId (200)	ethyl alcohol, fine yellow needles	62.3	4.3	9.1	62.5	4.5	8.9
2-Methyl-4'-cyano- (.145)	Indole (.120)	IVa (100)	alcohol, clusters of of needles	82.4	5.5	7.7	82.4	5.5	7.6
3-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-4'-cyano- (.145)	-do- (.120)	IVb (60)	alcohol, yellow needles	76.4	5.7	6.6	76.1	5.9	6.8
2-Methyl-3'-cyano- (.145)	-do- (.120)	IVc	152-54° alcohol, clusters of needles	82.4	5.5	7.7	82.6	5.6	7.4
4-Methoxy-4'-methyl- (.600)	Cyclohexanone (.500)	V (800)	133-34° alcohol, fine needles	78.8	7.5		78.4	7.6	

Hydrolysis of (15) to give 3-ethoxy-4-methoxy-3'-carboxychalkone : The chalkone (15) (200 mg) was refluxed with 5% sodium hydroxide solution for 4 hr. After cooling the mass was diluted first with ice cold water and then acidified. The solid which separated was filtered, washed well with water and dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution. The latter filtrate was acidified and the solid obtained (60 mg) was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (40–60°) in fine brick red needles, m.p. 143° (Found : C, 69.5; H, 5.4. $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 69.9; H, 5.5%).

Reaction of ethyl acetoacetate with 2-methyl-4'-cyanochalkone : To a solution of the above chalkone (200 mg) in alcohol (20 ml) was added 3–4 drops of ethyl acetoacetate and dry potassium carbonate (500 mg) and left overnight. The next day a colour change was noticed from pale yellow to pink. The reaction mixture was filtered, washed with alcohol and diluted. Steam was passed to remove unreacted ethyl acetoacetate and the aqueous residue was acidified with the minimum amount of acetic acid (1 : 1) to give I (80mg). (See Table III).

Reaction of chalkones with phenylhydrazine : The chalkone (1 g.) was added to phenylhydrazine (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) and refluxed for 3 hr. After cooling, the resultant mass was diluted with water to give III. (See Table III).

Reaction of chalkones with indole : A mixture of indole (120 mg) and the chalkone (145 mg) in acetic acid (6 ml.) and acetic anhydride (2 ml.) was kept on a water bath for 24 hr. and then decomposed with ice water (100 ml.). The dark coloured solid that separated was extracted with ether and the solvent layer was washed with water and dried. The solid obtained on removal of the solvent was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol to give IV. (See Table III).

Preparation of V : A solution of 4-methoxy-4'-methylchalkone (600 mg.) and cyclohexanone (500 mg) was added a solution of sodium hydroxide (750 mg.) in water (0.75 ml.) at 40°. The reaction mixture was kept overnight when V separated. It was filtered, washed with water and then with little alcohol. (See Table III).

Cyclisation of V to VI : The compound V (1 g.) was refluxed with glacial acetic acid (35 ml.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 ml.) and the heating continued for 42 hrs. Then water (20 ml.) was added and the brownish oil which separated was treated with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate and extracted with ether. The solvent layer was washed with water and dried and the solvent removed to give a yellow oily residue which on crystallisation from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether gave VI (300 mg.) as colourless needles, m.p. 160–61° (Found : C, 83.3; H, 7.4. $C_{23}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 83.1; H, 7.2%).

Oxime of VI : To a hot mixture of VI (1 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (500 mg.) and 95% alcohol (20 ml.) was added a solution of anhydrous sodium carbonate (750 mg.) in water (5 ml.) over a period of 20 mins. After 2 hrs. the solid which remained undissolved was broken up and additional water (5 ml.) was added and the heating continued for further 2.5 hr. On cooling the oxime separated as a crystalline solid. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight and the solid filtered and washed with water (15 ml.). It was crystallised from alcohol as needles m.p. 158–59° (Found : C, 79.5; H, 7.3. $C_{23}H_{25}NO_2$ requires C, 79.5; H, 7.2%).

Preparation of VII : *p*-Toluenesulphonyl chloride (360 mg.) was added in one portion to a solution of the oxime of VI (300 mg.) in pyridine (5 ml.) at room temperature and left overnight. The dark red solution was poured over ice water containing concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) and ether (10 ml.). The viscous mass which separated soon solidified and was filtered, washed with water and ether and crystallised from dilute methanol (60%) in fine colourless plates m.p. 138° (Found : C, 79.4; H, 7.0. $C_{23}H_{25}NO_2$ requires C, 79.5; H, 7.2%).

Preparation of VIIIa and VIIIb : A suspension of the lactam VII (1 g.) in water (40 ml.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (40 ml.) was heated under reflux with stirring for nine days. The solid which separated on cooling was filtered and dissolved in hot water (60 ml.) by adding dilute sodium hydroxide until the pH was approximately 6.0 (test paper). The solution was filtered to remove a small amount of insoluble material and then concentrated hydrochloric acid (25 ml.) was added to the hot filtrate when the hydrochloride began to separate. The mixture was cooled and filtered to give VIIIa (500 mg.) which decomposed gradually at 256°. It was purified by recrystallisation from aqueous hydrochloric acid as fine needles (Found : C, 73.8; H, 7.5. $C_{22}H_{28}NOCl$ requires C, 73.9; H, 7.6%).

The free base VIIIb was obtained by treatment of VIIIa with alkali, m.p. 70–72° (Found : N, 14.1. $C_{22}H_{27}NO$ requires N, 4.4).

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